

Methylene blue removal : An approach towards sludge management after adsorption of cadmium onto surfactant modified chitosan beads

Preeti Pal^a and Anjali Pal^{*b}

^aSchool of Environmental Science and Engineering, ^bCivil Engineering Department,
Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, Kharagpur-721 302, West Bengal, India

E-mail : pal.preeti@iitkgp.ac.in, anjalipal@civil.iitkgp.ac.in

Manuscript received 15 November 2017, revised 26 February 2018, accepted 13 March 2018

Abstract : In the present study chitosan (CS) beads were modified with the anionic surfactant (AS) to form surfactant modified chitosan (SMCS) beads. SMCS beads were used for the successful adsorption of cadmium ions (Cd^{2+}) from aqueous solution in the range of 10 to 100 mg/L with the maximum adsorption capacity of 125 mg/g. After adsorption of the Cd^{2+} onto SMCS beads, the adsorbent was named as cadmium loaded-SMCS (CdL-SMCS) beads. In order to manage the sludge remained after adsorption, CdL-SMCS beads were applied to the methylene blue (MB) solution (10–250 mg/L). Interestingly, CdL-SMCS beads loaded with different Cd^{2+} concentrations, showed 80–95% removal from MB solution. This led to conclude that even after adsorbing the Cd^{2+} , SMCS beads are able to remove nearly 95% MB dye with the Langmuir adsorption capacity of 500 mg/g.

Keywords : Chitosan, anionic surfactant, cadmium, methylene blue, adsorption.

I. Introduction

Due to the metropolitan growth and industrialisation, the environment is getting deteriorated by various contaminants. Among the plentiful contaminants, the dye waste from textile dyeing is one of the factors which is largely affecting our day to day life. Methylene blue (MB), which is most commonly used dyeing agent for cotton, wool, and silk can cause irritation in eyes of human as well as of animals if exposed to it. MB is effective in the treatment of methanoglobinemia and some other diseases which involve the injection of very low concentration of MB. Prolonged exposure of methylene blue either through the medicine injection or by any other means can seriously affect the central nervous system¹. Ramaraju *et al.* (2013) reported that annual production and use of dyestuffs is 7×10^5 tonnes². Of the total production, 5–10% of the dye is lost in industrial effluents which is ultimately going to the water bodies³.

One of the best ways to remove the dye or color-

ing agent from the aqueous solution is adsorption. Adsorption through cost-effective biosorbents is much popular these days because of their natural origin. Chitosan is an eminent biopolymer which has lot of applications in the field of environmental science including the removal of heavy metals and dyes from wastewater. The legitimate properties of chitosan makes it an attractive compound. It is used in the remediation of environment through various applications.

In the present study, the chitosan beads were first used for the removal of anionic surfactant (AS), sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS). Surfactant concentration used for the study was 6000 mg/L. This study was also supported by recently reported research of Pal *et al.* (2016), where CS beads were used for the removal of SDS and dye from water medium⁴. In the present work, beads loaded with SDS were designated as SMCS beads and were used for the removal of Cd^{2+} . Removal mechanism is based on the fact that, surfactants can form a bilayer (admicelle)^{5,6}

over the CS beads which modify the CS beads surface with the negatively charged groups. The bilayer (micelle like) structure formed over the CS beads can solubilize the organic molecules by the process of solubilization⁵⁻¹⁰. The same concept was applied to Cd²⁺ using SMCS beads, and as expected the SMCS beads were able to remove the Cd²⁺ from the aqueous solution very effectively. The study is also supported by the recent reports which showed the removal of Ni²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions using surfactant modified chitosan beads^{5,11}. Cadmium loaded-SMCS beads were then utilized for the sorption of MB in order to manage the sludge remained after Cd²⁺ adsorption. MB removal was not expected as because CdL-SMCS beads are having positive charge on the surface. Interestingly, CdL-SMCS showed efficient removal of the MB dye from aqueous solution. Schematic of the removal of SDS followed by Cd²⁺ and MB is shown in Fig. 1. The figure also shows the photographs of vials indicating the colour difference in the solutions before and after adsorption of MB.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents and instruments

Chitosan (CS) powder (75–85% deacetylated) (Sigma-Aldrich, India), cadmium salt (CdCl₂.H₂O) (Merck), acetic acid (Merck), NaOH (Fisher Scientific), SDS (Merck), methanol and methylene blue (Sigma-Aldrich) were used as received. Double distilled water was used for all the experiments.

Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (SPECTRASCAN UV 2600, Chemito, India) was used to record the absorbance of MB. Orbital shaking incubator (Remi, India) was used for maintaining agitation of 100 rpm and temperature 30°C. All IR spectra were recorded with Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (NEXUS-870, USA).

B. Preparation of sorbent

Step 1 : Fabrication of CS beads

For preparing the chitosan (CS) beads, CS solution was prepared by dissolving 3 g of CS powder in 250 mL of 7% acetic acid (AA). The solution was thoroughly stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer for 7–8 h till it becomes a homogenous solution. An

alkaline coagulating mixture was prepared by mixing H₂O, methanol, NaOH in the ratio of 4 : 5 : 1 w/w respectively as reported by Mitani *et al.* (1991)¹². CS solution was then added drop wise using 5 mL micro pipette into a precipitation bath containing 150 mL of alkaline coagulating solution. Spherical and uniform beads of 3.5–3.7 mm diameter were produced. CS beads were left undisturbed overnight and rinsed extensively with distilled water till the pH of washing is ~7.0.

Step 2 : Modification of CS beads to form SMCS beads

SMCS beads were prepared by applying the beads to the SDS solution of concentration 6000 mg/L^{5,11}. 250 beads were added in the beaker containing 100 mL of SDS solution having concentration 6000 mg/L. The beads were left undisturbed for three days. Due to the presence of SDS at a concentration much higher than its critical micelle concentration (CMC), it formed a bilayer over the surface of chitosan beads. Prepared adsorbent is called SMCS beads.

Step 3 : Cd²⁺ loading of SMCS beads

SMCS beads were used for Cd²⁺ removal in the range of 10–100 mg/L. As elaborated in our earlier report¹¹, these beads were efficient for Cd²⁺ removal. The Cd²⁺ loading observed in SMCS beads were 22.22, 44.45, 66.45, 100.94, 124.86 mg/g for 10, 20, 30, 50, 100 mg/L of initial Cd²⁺ concentration, respectively. The SMCS beads after Cd²⁺ removal at the initial concentration of 100 mg/L was designated as CdL-SMCS beads.

Step 4 : MB removal by CdL-SMCS beads

CdL-SMCS beads were used for the removal of MB from aqueous solution with the varying concentration range of 10–250 mg/L. MB stock solution of 1000 mg/L was prepared followed by the dilutions for making the working solutions in the range of 10–250 mg/L. CdL-SMCS beads were added to the MB solution (10–250 mg/L). After performing the experiments, the concentration of MB was calculated by the equation obtained from calibration curve of MB. λ_{max} was recorded at 663 nm by using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Different set of experiments were

performed to optimize the parameters and to compute the kinetic and adsorption isotherm constants.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the formation of CS beads and its modification with SDS for removal of Cd^{2+} to form CdL-SMCS beads followed by the adsorption of MB.

III. Results and discussion

A. Cadmium desorption study from CdL-SMCS beads

After adsorption of Cd^{2+} from the aqueous solution, desorption study was performed and it was found that it is not desorbing in the range of pH 4–8. As chitosan is a biosorbent, both chemical and physical adsorption takes place over it. Hence, desorption from the SMCS beads was very less (~16–20%). It confirms that Cd^{2+} is strongly attached to the SMCS beads. In order to use the waste beads which are having the 80–90% of Cd^{2+} inside and over the SMCS beads, MB adsorption study was performed with CdL-SMCS beads.

B. MB adsorption on CdL-SMCS beads

(1) Evaluation of the CS and CdL-SMCS beads for the removal of MB

Preliminary study was performed on MB removal with CS beads and Cd^{2+} loaded (loading : 125 mg of Cd^{2+} per g of SMCS) SMCS beads. Fig. 2 shows the comparison of the uptake capacity (mg/g) of MB from aqueous solution. It can be inferred from the graph that the uptake capacity of Cd^{2+} loaded SMCS beads is much higher than that of CS beads. The adsorption capacity shown by the Cd^{2+} loaded SMCS beads for initial concentration of 250 mg/L of MB is 366.13 mg/g while CS beads showed the capacity only 64.36 mg/g. Adsorption is ~5 times higher in case of CdL-SMCS beads compared to that of CS beads. Hence, it leads us to explore the other parameters for MB removal.

Fig. 2. Evaluation of the CS and Cd^{2+} loaded SMCS beads (125 mg/g) for removal of MB. [MB] : 10–250 mg/L, adsorbent dose : 0.45 g/L, time : 72 h, agitation speed : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C.

(2) Selection of beads after Cd^{2+} loading

CdL-SMCS beads with different Cd^{2+} loading in the range of 10–100 mg/L were assessed for MB uptake capacity. It is shown in Fig. 3 that when the SMCS beads were treated with Cd^{2+} at initial concentrations 10, 20 and 30 mg/L the beads resulted in almost 80% removal of MB. On the other hand when the SMCS beads were treated with Cd^{2+} solutions at initial concentration 50–100 mg/L, the beads could lead to the removal of nearly 98–100% of MB. It

can be concluded from the results that somehow, presence of Cd^{2+} in CdL-SMCS beads enhances the removal of MB. For further studies the SMCS beads treated with Cd^{2+} solution having initial concentration 100 mg/L were selected for preparation of CdL-SMCS beads.

Fig. 3. Effect of Cd^{2+} loading on removal of MB by CdL-SMCS beads. [MB] : 50 mg/L; dose : 0.45 g/L, time : 72 h, agitation : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C.

(3) Effect of contact time on adsorption of MB

Effect of contact time was investigated by performing the experiment at different interval of time. MB adsorption onto the CdL-SMCS beads was observed to be a slow process; hence time chosen for the kinetic study was 1 min to 96 h. The samples were collected at different interval of time. Fig. 4 shows the graph of kinetic study. It can be interpreted from the graph that time taken for MB removal is 70–72 h. In the time span of 72 h, CdL-SMCS beads are able to capture 90–95% of MB. Hence, 72 h contact time was chosen as the optimum time for equilibrium studies. Similar results were also observed in the study of Das and Pal⁶, where, chitosan-surfactant composite took 96 h for removal of malachite green. Tests for Cd^{2+} and SDS leaching in the samples were also performed but interestingly, there was a negligible (only 5–6%) leaching of both (data not shown).

(4) Effect of dose on adsorption of MB

Experiment was performed in order to optimize the dose which is suitable for maximum removal of MB from the solution. For this particular study MB concentration was fixed as 50 mg/L, with the vary-

Fig. 4. Time dependency on removal of MB using CdL-SMCS beads. [MB] : 50 mg/L, dose : 0.45 g/L, agitation : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C.

ing doses of CdL-SMCS in the range 0.09–1.135 g/L. After adding beads to the MB solution, it was kept at 30°C in incubator shaker for 72 h. Results of the study are shown in Fig. 5. Graph indicates that the dose >0.45 g/L is suitable for the removal of 90–95% of MB from the solution. After 0.675 g/L dose, % removal is almost saturated. Hence, we can conclude that the dose between 0.45–0.675 g/L is enough for removal of ~95% of MB with 50 mg/L initial concentration.

Fig. 5. Effect of adsorbent dosage on removal of MB by CdL-SMCS beads. [MB] : 50 mg/L, time : 72 h, agitation speed : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C.

(5) Effect of MB concentration on % removal efficiency of CdL-SMCS beads

To explore the dependence of MB concentration on the removal process by CdL-SMCS, the initial concentration of MB was taken in the range of 10–250 mg/L. CdL-SMCS was added to the 10 mL vol-

ume of MB solution and kept at 100 rpm in incubator shaker for the optimized contact time of 72 h. It was found that from 250 mg/L of MB, CdL-SMCS beads were able to remove nearly 50% while for <50 mg/L of MB, the beads were able to remove almost 95% of the dye. The results are graphed in Fig. 6, where photograph of MB loaded beads are also shown along with the vials, clearly indicating the removal of MB.

Beads were weighed before and after MB adsorption and the results are shown in Table 1. Result depicts that MB adsorption onto the CdL-SMCS beads is responsible for adding up some weight to the adsorbent.

Table 1. Weight of the adsorbent before and after the adsorption of MB

Beads type	Weight per bead (g)	
	Wet weight	Dry weight
CdL-SMCS (before adsorption)	2.58×10^{-2}	9.0×10^{-4}
MBL-SMCS after adsorption	2.64×10^{-2}	9.3×10^{-4}

Fig. 6. Effect of MB concentration on its removal by CdL-SMCS beads. [MB] : 10–250 mg/L, dose : 0.45 g/L, time : 72 h, agitation speed : 100 rpm. The photograph showing (a) SMCS beads, (b) CdL-SMCS beads, (c) 10 mg/L MB loaded beads and (d) 50 mg/L MB loaded beads.

C. Kinetic study

Kinetic study helps us to find out the mechanism of the adsorption between adsorbent and adsorbate. Generally adsorption process follows pseudo-second order mechanism, which suggests that the process is dominated by chemisorption^{13,14}. Kinetic data were

applied to the most widely used pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order models. Kinetic equations and their linearised forms are given in Table 2, where q_t (mg/g) and q_e (mg/g) are the amount of MB adsorbed on the CdL-SMCS beads at time t and at equilibrium, respectively; k_{S1} (min^{-1}) and k_{S2} ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) are the rate constants of the pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model, respectively. Initial concentration of MB for the study was selected as 50 mg/L with the adsorbent dosage of 0.45 g/L, kept at 100 rpm maintaining the temperature $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Results acquired for the kinetic study depicts that the adsorption process follows pseudo-second order kinetic model. This conclusion can be made from the R^2 values. As the adsorption follows the pseudo-second order model, it concludes that the sorption of MB onto CdL-SMCS beads is chemisorption over the heterogeneous surface of the beads.

Fig. 7. Kinetics on MB removal by CdL-SMCS beads. (a) The fitting of pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order model and (b) plot of q_t vs t for experimental data and calculated values of q_e (based on the pseudo-second order model). [MB] : 50 mg/L, dose : 0.45 g/L, time : 72 h, agitation : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C .

Table 2. Pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order rate constants of MB adsorption onto the CdL-SMCS beads with their linearized equations and R^2 values

Model	Pseudo-first order	Pseudo-second order
Linear equation	$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_{S1} t$	$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_{S2} q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e}$
Graph plotted	$\ln (q_e - q_t)$ vs t	$\frac{t}{q_t}$ vs t
Equation of linear fit line	$\ln (q_e - q_t) = -0.0009x + 3.6812$	$t/q_t = 0.0097x + 0.4675$
R^2	0.8785	0.999
q_e (mg/g)	39.69	103.09
Constant (k)	$k_{S1} = 9.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (min ⁻¹)	$k_{S2} = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (g mg ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)

D. Equilibrium adsorption isotherm study

Equilibrium study illustrates the mobility of adsorbate towards the adsorbent from aqueous media to the solid surface at constant temperature and pH¹⁵. To know the interaction between the MB and CdL-SMCS beads, capacity (mg/g) and the adsorption mechanism, the equilibrium studies were carried out. The data obtained were fitted with the most popular Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. The equations obtained and the computed parameters with the R^2 values are given in Table 3. On the basis of R^2 value it can be concluded that the adsorption data between the MB and CdL-SMCS complied with the Freundlich isotherm. Freundlich describes the reversible and multilayer adsorption over the adsorbent with non-uniform distribution. Adsorption intensity obtained here is 0.516 which indicates that surface is hetero-

geneous and it also implies that the adsorption is chemisorption^{15,16}. Adsorption equilibrium data obtained are graphed in Fig. 8 (a) and (b), which shows the exactness with the Freundlich model.

E. FTIR analysis of MB loaded CdL-SMCS beads (MBL-SMCS) and CdL-SMCS beads

The FTIR spectra of CdL-SMCS and MBL-SMCS beads are shown in Fig. 9. The characteristic band observed near about 1670 cm⁻¹ in CdL-SMCS, is due to the stretching vibrations of C=O. Major change observed after adsorption of MB dye was splitting of (C=O) stretching into small splits (1670 cm⁻¹, 1604 cm⁻¹, 1539 cm⁻¹). 1604 cm⁻¹ is the stretching vibration of aromatic ring of MB¹⁷. The splitting is expected due to the interactions between MB and adsorbent^{3,18}. The spectra of MBL-SMCS beads showed new peaks which were absent in CdL-SMCS beads.

Table 3. Adsorption isotherm model equations, values of isotherm constants and their corresponding R^2 values

Model	Parameters	Values
Langmuir isotherm model	Equation	$C_e/q_e = 0.002C_e + 0.062$
	q_{max} (mg/g) (Maximum adsorption capacity)	500.0
	K_L	0.0323
	R^2	0.922
	Freundlich isotherm model	Equation
	k_f [(mg/g)(L/mg) ^{1/n}] (constant related to adsorption capacity)	28.76
	$1/n$ (adsorption intensity)	0.516
	R^2	0.985

Fig. 8. Langmuir (a) and Freundlich (b) adsorption isotherm model for removal of MB using CdL-SMCS beads. [MB] : 10–250 mg/L, dose : 0.45 g/L, time : 72 h, agitation : 100 rpm, temperature : 30°C.

Table 4. Interpretation of the peaks obtained by the FTIR spectra of the CdL-SMCS and MBL-SMCS beads

Wave numbers (cm ⁻¹)	Characteristic band	Reference
1604	C=C	[3]
1539	C=C of aromatic compound	[3]
1337	CH ₃ (of MB)	[17]
1014	C-O stretching	[18]
890	-NH ₂	[19]
808	-C-H-	[20]

The peaks at 1539 cm⁻¹ confirms the presence of aromatic bonds of (C=C) in MBL-SMCS³. The vibrations of the CH₃ group of MB were found at 1356 and 1337 cm⁻¹ which is also confirmed by Xiong *et al.*¹⁷. The band at 890 cm⁻¹ on CdL-SMCS as well as MBL-SMCS beads is the vibration of NH₂¹⁹. It is predominating in CdL-SMCS beads while after MB adsorption the peaks are weak and small. Several weak peaks between 1014 and 550 cm⁻¹ were ascribed to the C-H bending vibrations¹⁷ (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. FTIR spectra of CdL-SMCS and MBL-SMCS beads.

IV. Conclusion

Herein, we report a simple method of synthesizing the surfactant-modified chitosan (SMCS) beads for the removal of Cd^{2+} . The material is broadly suitable for the removal of positively charged pollutants because of the modification by anionic surfactant over the surface of chitosan (CS) beads. The waste material generated after the removal of Cd^{2+} on the SMCS beads have shown the promise for the removal of MB from the aqueous solution. Cadmium loaded-SMCS beads prepared using initial Cd^{2+} concentration of 100 mg/L was used as the adsorbent for MB removal. These beads were designated as CdL-SMCS beads. Solution pH range 6–7 and agitation at 100 rpm at a constant temperature of 30°C were the optimized parameters for the MB removal. CdL-SMCS beads showed 50–95% MB removal from the aqueous solution in the concentration range of 10–250 mg/L with the dosage of 0.45 g/L. Langmuir adsorption capacity obtained was 500.0 mg/g which is much better compared to those obtained in the reported studies. Kinetic data complied with the pseudo-second order model. Equilibrium adsorption data fitted well with the Freundlich isotherm which confirms the multilayer adsorption. Thus, since CdL-SMCS beads could be successfully used for the MB dye removal, hence we can conclude that the developed sludge after Cd^{2+} removal by SMCS could be used for the wastewater treatment as a multi-functional adsorbent. CS beads prepared in this work have been used successively for the removal SDS, Cd^{2+} , and MB.

References

1. L. Vutskits, A. Briner, P. Klauser, E. Gascon, A. G. Dayer, J. Z. Kiss, D. Muller, M. J. Licker and D. R. Morel, *Anesthesiology*, 2008, **108**, 684.
2. B. Ramaraju, P. Manoj Kumar Reddy and C. Subrahmanyam, *Environ. Prog. Sustain. Energy*, 2014, **33**, 38.
3. D. L. Postai, C. A. Demarchi, F. Zanatta, D. C. C. Melo and C. A. Rodrigues, *Alexandria Eng. J.*, 2016, **55**, 1713.
4. A. Pal, S. Pan and S. Saha, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2013, **217**, 426.
5. R. J. Kongarapu, P. Mahamallik and A. Pal, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, 2017, **5**, 1321.
6. D. Das and A. Pal, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2016, **290**, 371.
7. M. Bielska and J. Szymanowski, *Water Res.*, 2006, **40**, 1027.
8. G. M. Zeng, X. Li, J. H. Huang, C. Zhang, C. F. Zhou, J. Niu, L. J. Shi, S. B. He and F. Li, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2011, **185**, 1304.
9. A. Adak, A. Pal and M. Bandyopadhyay, *Colloids Surfaces A : Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, 2006, **277**, 63.
10. A. R. Cestari, E. F. S. Vieira and J. A. Mota, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2008, **160**, 337.
11. P. Pal and A. Pal, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2017, **104**, 1548.
12. T. Mitani, N. Fukumuro, C. Yoshimoto and H. Ishii, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1991, **55**, 2419.
13. Y. F. Lin, H. W. Chen, P. S. Chien, C. S. Chiou and C. C. Liu, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2011, **185**, 1124.
14. S. Saber-Samandari, S. Saber-Samandari, N. Nezafati and K. Yahya, *J. Environ. Manage.*, 2014, **146**, 481.
15. K. Y. Foo and B. H. Hameed, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2010, **156**, 2.
16. F. Haghseresht and G. Q. Lu, *Energy & Fuels*, 1998, **12**, 1100.
17. L. Xiong, Y. Yang, J. Mai, W. Sun, C. Zhang, D. Wei, Q. Chen and J. Ni, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2010, **156**, 313.
18. R. Gottipati and S. Mishra, *Brazilian J. Chem. Eng.*, 2010, **27**, 357.
19. J. O. Akinyeye, T. B. Ibigbami and O. Odeja, *Am. J. Appl. Chem.*, 2016, **4**, 146.
20. N. Qutub, B. M. Pirzada, K. Umar and S. Sabir, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, 2016, **4**, 808.